

Kinetics of the Reaction between Lactic Acid and Chromium Peroxydichromate. Part I

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A search of the literature reveals that the oxidation of lactic acid by different oxidising agents has been studied by several workers¹⁻¹⁹. Kinetics of oxidation of different organic acids by chromium peroxydichromate has been studied by Rai and coworkers^{20,21}. In view of the above, the authors have studied the kinetics of oxidation of lactic acid by chromium peroxydichromate.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either AnalaR or extra pure quality and the solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Chromium peroxydichromate was prepared as described earlier²² and was standardised against standard sodium thiosulphate.

The reaction kinetics between lactic acid and peroxydichromate was studied at different temperatures in a thermostat with possible variation of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The progress of the reaction was studied by estimating the unreacted oxidant i.e., $(a-x)$ at different intervals of time using same sodiumthiosulphate solution.

The reaction order was determined by the Ostwald's isolation and fractional life period methods. The timings for half and three fourth change in concentration of oxidant were determined graphically, from the plot of $(a-x)$ vs. t (in minutes).

The values for the rate constants for first order reaction were found to be constant and was also confirmed by partial reaction time ratio²².

$$\frac{t_f'}{t_f''} = \frac{\log(1-f')}{\log(1-f'')} \text{ for first order} \quad \dots (1)$$

t_f' and t_f'' being the timings for the fractional changes f' and f'' respectively. The equation (1) for three-fourths and half change is reduced as :

$$\frac{t_{3/4}}{t_{1/2}} = 2 \quad \dots (2)$$

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

TABLE 1

Effect of lactic acid and temperature
 Peroxydichromate 0.025N

Temp. °C	Lactic acid N	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min. ⁻¹	$k \times 10^2$ mole ⁻² litre. ² min. ⁻¹	$t_{1/2}$ min.	$t_{3/4}$ min.	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min. ⁻¹ from $t_{1/2}$	$\frac{t_{3/4}}{t_{1/2}}$
20	0.3	1.426	15.84	48.5	97.0	1.429	2.00
	0.4	2.415	15.09	28.7	58.0	2.415	2.02
	0.5	3.704	14.81	18.7	38.0	3.707	2.03
25	0.3	1.905	21.17	37.0	74.0	1.872	2.00
	0.4	3.223	20.14	21.5	44.0	3.224	2.04
	0.5	4.749	18.99	15.0	30.0	4.621	2.00
30	0.3	2.611	29.01	26.5	53.0	2.615	2.00
	0.4	4.527	28.29	15.0	30.5	4.621	2.03
	0.5	7.024	28.09	9.8	19.8	7.073	2.02
35	0.3	3.676	40.84	19.0	38.0	3.648	2.00
	0.4	6.321	39.50	10.8	22.0	6.418	2.03
	0.5	9.725	39.00	7.2	14.4	9.627	2.00

Above observations show that the reaction is first order with respect to oxidant i.e., chromium peroxydichromate and two with respect to lactic acid as $k_1/(\text{Lactic acid})^2$ i.e., K_s is fairly constant at each temperature.

TABLE 2

Effect of peroxydichromate and temperature

Temp. °C	Lactic acid N	Oxidant N	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min. ⁻¹	$t_{1/2}$ min.	$t_{3/4}$ min.	$\frac{t_{3/4}}{t_{1/2}}$
20	0.5	0.00625	3.694	18.7	37.5	2.00
		0.0125	3.668	19.0	38.5	2.02
25		0.00625	4.737	14.8	29.5	1.99
		0.0125	4.649	15.2	30.0	1.98
30		0.00625	6.807	10.0	20.1	2.01
		0.0125	6.827	10.1	20.0	1.98
	0.4	0.00625	4.563	15.1	31.0	2.05
		0.0125	4.527	15.2	30.5	2.00

Values of k_1 and timings for fractional change are independent the concentration of the oxidant which shows that the reaction is completely isolated, and first order with respect to oxidant.

TABLE 3
The comparative effect of acids

Acid <i>N</i>	Lactic acid 0.4 <i>N</i>		Temperature 25°				Oxidant 0.025 <i>N</i>		
	Sulphuric $k_1 \times 10^2$	t_1	Hydrochloric		Phosphoric		Acetic		
			$k_1 \times 10^2$	t_1	$k_1 \times 10^2$	t_1	$k_1 \times 10^2$	t_1	
0.0625	6.778	10.5	7.053	8.8	—	—	—	—	
0.125	9.192	7.7	11.01	6.3	4.134	17.0	3.919	17.5	
0.250	12.61	5.5	13.96	5.0	3.976	17.5	3.980	17.5	
0.500	16.40	4.3	13.53	5.3	3.368	20.5	3.992	17.5	
1.000	—	—	10.12	7.0	2.877	25.0	4.101	17.0	

The comparative effect of various acids is shown in the above table. By increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid the reaction rate increases, In the case of hydrochloric acid, the reaction rate increases in the beginning up to a certain concentration (0.25 *N*), but on further increase in concentration of hydrochloric acid formation of chlorochromate²³ ion takes place, which causes the retardation, being less efficient oxidant. In the case of phosphoric acid, the reaction rate is slightly enhanced at lower concentrations, but at higher concentrations the reaction rate is retarded. In the case of acetic acid, the reaction rate is nearly constant.

TABLE 4
Effect of Manganous Sulphate

Lactic acid 0.3 <i>N</i>	Manganous sulphate <i>M</i>	Temperature 25°			Oxidant 0.025 <i>N</i>
		$k_1 \times 10^2$	$t_{1/2}$	$t_{3/4}$	$\frac{t_{3/4}}{t_{1/2}}$
	0.001	2.098	31.0	60.0	1.93
	0.002	2.366	29.5	58.0	1.96
	0.004	2.468	28.0	54.0	1.92
	0.010	2.792	26.0	48.0	1.84

The reaction rate increases with increase in concentration of manganous sulphate.

The plot of $\log k_s$ vs $1/T$ is found a straight line. The energy of activation calculated from the slope of the line was found to be 11.59 Kcals/mole.

TABLE 5
Activation Parameters

Lactic acid 0.4 N		Oxidant 0.025 N		
Temp. between	Temp. Coefficient	Energy of activation Kcals/mole	Frequency factor mole ⁻² litre ² sec. ⁻¹	Entropy of activation E.U.
20°—30°	1.875	11.09	4.66 × 10 ⁶	-32.59
25°—35°	1.961	12.28	3.39 × 10 ⁶	-28.73

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